

Radionuclide Actions, Processes and Presence in Water and Sediments, a Review

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Abstract: This study was carried out to review the actions of radionuclides, their formation processes and presence in water and sediments. Although since its discovery it has been found to play some negative role on man's health and destruction the solid part of the earth where man depends for his survival through agriculture. Hence this study focused on reviewing the works of other writers as to ascertain the role, sources, presences and action as well as the processes of radionuclide formation. The review showed that radionuclides are the sources of radioactivity and emit nuclear radiation which has become a part of our daily lives. The most common forms of ionizing radiation (released energy) are alpha particles, beta particles and gamma rays. The properties of radiations have wide applications in areas such as medicine, biology, industry, agriculture, and electric power generation. There are numerous health hazard associated with radiation exposure due to an overdose of it. The study also discovered that its sources occur from both natural and manmade and that different methods are applied in determining the presence of radionuclide and that some equipments have also been developed over the years that are used for detecting radionuclide. The study concluded that having understood that radionuclides occur through anthropogenic activities and noting its health effects, there is need to guide activities that bring about its existence and set in policies that could reduce actions that ignite its natural occurring process.

Keywords: Radionuclides, Actions, Processes, Presence, Sediments, Water

Introduction

The science of radioactivity has been extensively studied since the discovery of radioactivity in 1896 by A. H. Becquerel (Allisy, 1996). The earth has been radioactive ever since its formation into a solid mass over 4.5 billion years ago. Nevertheless, the knowledge about radiation and radioactivity is just over one hundred years. Long-lived radioactive elements such as uranium, thorium and potassium and any of their decay products, such as radium and radon are

examples of NORM. These elements have always been present in the Earth's crust and atmosphere, and are concentrated in some places, such as uranium ore bodies which may be mined

The early discovery of naturally occurring radiation and environmental radioactivity has led to an extensive survey in many countries all over the world (UNSCEAR, 2000). Such investigations can be useful for both the assessment of public dose rates and the performance of epidemiological studies, as well as to keep reference–data records, to determine possible alterations in the environment radioactivity due to nuclear, industrial, and other human activities.

Radionuclides are the sources of radioactivity and emit nuclear radiation which have become a part of our daily lives. The most common forms of ionizing radiation (released energy) are alpha particles, beta particles and gamma rays (Lilley, 2001). Radiation can result not only from natural radionuclides but it can also be from man-made sources. The characteristics of radiations have broad applications in areas such as medicine, biology, industry, agriculture, and electric power generation (Eisenbud and Gesell, 1997). As a consequence of the applications of radiation, human beings can be exposed to the radiation emitting from various radioactive sources depending upon their activities and surroundings (Klement, 1982). Nevertheless, not all of the population is subjected to all the various sources of radiation exposure. For instance, patients who are treated with medical irradiation or members of staff who work in the nuclear industries may receive more radiation exposure levels than members of the general public (Watson et al, 2005).

Radioactivity concentrations in sediment and water samples can be detected through different methods using various techniques.

Primordial radionuclides are formed by the process of nucleosynthesis in stars and are characterized by half–lives comparable to the age of the earth (Tzortzis et al, 2003). The interactions of cosmic-ray particles in the atmosphere can create some radioactive nuclei such as ^3H , ^7Be , and ^{14}C (NCRP, 1975). The other main contributor is the terrestrial radioactive materials that originate from the formation of the earth and are ubiquitous in the earth's crust, and in the human body itself. These radionuclides are known as Naturally Occurring Radioactive Material or '*NORM*' (WNA, 2011, Wilson, 1994). Only very long lived nuclides, with decay half-lives comparable to the age of the earth, and their decay products, contribute to this natural radiation background in significant quantities (UNSCEAR 2000). The majority of naturally occurring radionuclides belong to the radionuclides in the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th series, and the single decay radionuclide, ^{40}K which occurs at trace levels in all geologic formations (IAEA, 2003). See Table 1.

Table 1: Ranges and averages of the concentrations of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in typical rocks and soils (Eisenbud and Gesell, 1997, IAEA, 2003)

Rock Type	Potassium-40		Thorium-232		Uranium-238	
	Total K (%)	Bq.kg-1	ppm	Bq.kg-1	ppm	Bq.kg-1
Igneous rocks						
Basalt						
Crustal average	0.8	300	3-4	10-15	0.5-1	7-10
Mafic	0.3-1.1	70-400	1.6, 2.7	7	0.5, 0.9	7
Salic	4.5	1100-1500	16, 20	60	3.9, 4.7	50
Granite						
(crustal aver.)	>4	>1000	17	70	3	40
Sedimentary rocks						
Shale, sandstones						
Clean quartz	<1	<300	<2	<8	<1	<10
Dirty quartz	2	400	3-6	10-25	2-3	40
Arkose	2-3	600-900	2	<8	1-2	10-25
Beach sands	<1	<300	6	25	3	40
(unconsolidated)						
Carbonate rocks						
	0.3	70	2	8	2	25
All rock (range)						
	0.3-4.5	700-1500	1.6-20	7-80	0.5-4.7	7-60
Continental						
crust (ave.)	2.8	850	10.7	44	2.8	36
Soil (ave.)	1.5	400	9	37	1.8	22

Those radionuclides which emit either alpha or beta particles may get into the human body by ingestion or inhalation and can result in internal exposures. Also, some of these nuclear species may emit gamma rays following their radioactive decay; these represent the main sources of external (whole body) exposures to humans (Watson et al, 2005, UNSCEAR, 2000).

Scholars, from both the developed and developing nations of the world, have worked extensively in ascertaining the activity concentration of radionuclides in various sources of water and different types of soil, as it affects community health (Strain and Watson, 1979). This has been of assistance in calculating the annual collective effective dose due to exposure through ingestion or inhalation.

Sources of Radionuclide

The radionuclide origin in the environment can be divided into two main sources: (i) natural and (ii) man-made sources. The naturally occurring radiation comes mainly from terrestrial radioactive nuclides which are broadly distributed in the earth's crust and extra-terrestrial sources arising from cosmic ray bombardment (Lilley, 2001; Eisenbud and Gesell, 1975; Klement, 1982; UNSCEAR, 2000; NCRP, 1975). Other sources come from human activities concerned with the usage of radiation and radioactive materials from which releases of radionuclides into the environment may occur.

Natural Sources

The naturally occurring radioactive material or NORM which results to radiation exposure for humans surrounding are comprised isotopes that occur individually or are components of the three main radioactive decay series (Eisenbud and Gesell, 1975. NCRP, 1975). These radionuclides can be classified into two types, the primordial and cosmogenic, in relation to their origin.

Primordial Radionuclides

The radionuclides which are of terrestrial origin and have been on earth since its formation are known as primordial radionuclides. These radionuclides have very long decay half-lives, comparable to the age of the earth (Lilley, 2001; Klement, 1982; Watson et al, 2005; Wilson, 1994). They are everywhere in the earth's crust, and are consequently assumed to represent a primordial inventory. The primordial radionuclides can be further sub-classified into the *series* and *non-series* radionuclides (Eisenbud and Gesell, 1975; NCRP, 1975). The major primordial radionuclides are listed in Table 2.

Non-Series Radionuclides

Several primordial radionuclides are in the *non-series* group that decays directly to stable nuclides as shown in Table 2. Most of these have extremely long half-lives and very low isotopic abundance, resulting in their negligibly small activities, which means that they are normally not considered as important in terms of radiation exposure to humans. However, two such isotopes, ^{40}K and ^{87}Rb , are significant sources of natural radiation. ^{40}K can decay by beta followed by gamma-ray emission whereas ^{87}Rb is a pure beta emitter (Eisenbud and Gesell, 1997; NCRP, 1975).

Series Radionuclides

There are four major radioactive decay series, namely the *Uranium*, *Thorium*, *Actinium*, and *Neptunium* series (Lilley, 2001; Lapp. and Andrews, (1972). These chains are headed by the heavy isotopes ^{238}U , ^{232}Th , ^{235}U , and ^{237}Np respectively. The non-existence of the head of the Neptunium series and relatively short half-life daughters means that this series does not count as part of the natural radioactivity decay chains on earth. The three significant remaining chains of radioactive nuclides decay through sequences of radioactive daughter nuclides with a wide range of half-lives and finally reach a stable isotope of lead at the end of each chain. The principal decay schemes of three radioactive series and the details of each radionuclide within the chains are shown and presented in Figure 2.

**Table 2: List of Primordial Radionuclide's
(Eisenbud and Gesell, 2009; Watson et al, 2005; UNSCEAR, 2000)**

Nuclide	Decay Mode	Half-life (years)	Isotopic Abundance (%)	Stable Disintegration Products
⁴⁰ K	β, ε, γ	1.3 x 10 ⁹	0.0117	⁴⁰ Ar, ⁴⁰ Ca
⁵⁰ V	β, ε, γ	1.4 x 10 ¹⁷	0.25	⁵⁰ V, ⁵⁰ Ti
⁸⁷ Rb	β	4.9 x 10 ¹⁰	27.83	⁸⁷ Sr
¹¹³ Cd	β	7.7 x 10 ¹⁵	12.22	¹¹³ In
¹¹⁵ In	β	4.4 x 10 ¹⁴	95.71	¹¹⁵ Sn
¹²³ Te	ε	6.0 x 10 ¹⁴	0.89	¹²³ Sb
¹³⁸ La	β, ε, γ	1.1 x 10 ¹¹	0.09	¹³⁸ Ba, ¹³⁸ Ce
¹⁴⁴ Nd	α	2.4 x 10 ¹⁵	23.80	¹⁴⁰ Ce
¹⁴⁷ Sm	α	1.1 x 10 ¹¹	14.99	¹⁴³ Nd
¹⁴⁸ Sm	α	7.0 x 10 ¹⁵	11.24	¹⁴⁴ Nd
¹⁵² Gd	α	1.1 x 10 ¹⁴	0.20	¹⁴⁸ Sm
¹⁷⁴ Hf	α	2.0 x 10 ¹⁵	0.16	¹⁷⁰ Yb
¹⁷⁶ Lu	β, γ	3.8 x 10 ¹⁰	2.59	¹⁷⁶ Hf
¹⁸⁶ Os	α	2.0 x 10 ¹⁵	1.59	¹⁸² W
¹⁸⁷ Re	β	4.1 x 10 ¹⁰	62.60	¹⁸⁷ Os
¹⁹⁰ Pt	α	6.5 x 10 ¹¹	0.014	¹⁸⁶ Os
²³⁸ U(series)	α	4.5 x 10 ⁹	99.27	²⁰⁶ Pb
²³⁵ U(series)	α	7.0 x 10 ⁸	0.72	²⁰⁷ Pb
²³² Th(series)	α	1.4 x 10 ¹⁰	100	²⁰⁸ Pb

Cosmic Radiation and Radionuclide Formation

Radioactivity in term of cosmic radiation comes from both the primary energetic protons and alpha particles of extraterrestrial origin that strike the earth's atmosphere and the secondary particles or cosmogenic radionuclides which are continuously generated by bombardment of stable nuclides in the atmosphere from these cosmic rays (Watson et al, 2005; NCRP, 1975).

Cosmogenic Radionuclides

Most of the principal cosmogenic radionuclides are produced continuously by the interaction of nucleons released from cosmic radiation with target nuclei in the earth atmosphere, mostly upper atmosphere (NCRP, 1975; Cember and Johnson, 2009). These interactions lead to a variety of spallation or neutron capture reactions (Klement, 1982; UNSCEAR, 2000). Spallation and charge exchange results in lighter or the same mass radionuclides being created compared with the target atom. Contrastingly, the products of neutron capture are radionuclides which have one

mass unit heavier than the original stable ‘target’ nuclide. The majority of target atoms in the earth’s atmosphere are from argon, oxygen, and nitrogen gases.

A great number of cosmic-ray produced radioactive isotopes can be found all around the earth. There are several cosmogenic radionuclides with a range of half-lives from minutes to millions of years; however, only four of them contribute a significant measurable dose of radioactivity to humans. From a radiation health aspect, the main cosmogenic radionuclides are tritium (3h), beryllium-7 (7be), carbon-14 (14c) and sodium-22 (22na). The most significant cosmogenic radionuclide is 14c which can be taken up by plants and becomes enter the food chain (Watson et al, 2005).

Anthropogenic Sources

Many radionuclides have been released into the environment due to the use of radiation sources by man for various purposes (Klement, 1982). Detectable quantities of man-made radionuclides are widely distributed in the atmosphere, particularly as a result of nuclear weapons testing and the Chernobyl reactor accident in 1986. A significant radionuclide produced from these sources is ^{137}Cs with half-life of 30.7 years. This nuclide has been globally dispersed and deposited through rain and dry deposition on terrestrial surfaces. It can be taken up by plants and subsequently be incorporated into foodstuffs. However, the environmental levels of released radionuclides are slowly declining and some of them are below the limits of detection. Other sources may be released from nuclear power fuel cycle (Lilley, 2001).

Radionuclides Presence and Occurrence in Sediments and Water

Radionuclides occur naturally as trace elements in rocks, soil, and ground water as a consequence of the radioactive decay of uranium and thorium. This decay occurs because these elements are unstable; they continually release energy into the environment until a stable, non radioactive substance is formed. This energy is part of the natural radiation to which all living creatures are exposed. Radon, radium, and uranium are the most common radioactive elements found in ground water. Other naturally occurring radionuclides tend to be environmentally immobile or have short half lives, meaning they are far less likely to be found in significant amounts in ground water.

Radiation plays an important role in our life. All living organisms are continually exposed to ionizing radiation, which has always existed naturally. The sources of exposure are cosmic rays, terrestrial radionuclides in the Earth’s crust, their presence in building materials and in the air, water and foods, and those present in the human body itself. In addition, exposure may arise from man-made radionuclides released into the terrestrial and marine environment (Nikolov et al., 2011). The largest contributor of ionizing radiation to the population is natural radioactivity.

The presence of natural radiation is due to the distribution of radionuclides on earth and causes exposure to all living organisms. There are three primordial radioactive decay chains in the earth’s crust: the thorium chain starting with ^{232}Th , the uranium chain starting with ^{238}U , and the

actinium chain starting with ^{235}U (McKittrick et al., 2003). The radium isotope ^{226}Ra and its decay product ^{222}Rn are produced from decay chain of ^{238}U . ^{222}Rn emits alpha particles as it spontaneously decays to a series of short-lived radioactive decay products, which are followed by a longer-lived series headed by ^{210}Pb (half-life, 22.3 y), as shown in Figure 2 (WNA, 2011). Of the four isotopes, ^{226}Ra causes the most concern due to a combination of its long half-life (1600 years) and radiological effects. It is among the most toxic long-lived-emitters present in environmental samples, as well as one of the most widespread (López et al., 2002). High solubility of this element compared with uranium causing penetration through fractures into bedrock and can leak out into groundwater. Radium-226 is a bone seeker element and can cause bone marrow cancer (Kearfott, 1989).

The greatest health risk from radium is from exposure to its radioactive decay product, radon. Radon is a major cause, second only to cigarette smoking, of lung cancer deaths. ^{226}Ra and its decay products can be brought up to earth surface by the water of warm springs. When the groundwater reaches the surface at hot spring locations, travertine, a calcium carbonate mineral, precipitates out of solution with dissolved radium substituting for calcium in the mineral. A secondary cause of high local radiation levels is travertine deposits with a high thorium concentration. The radioactivity in local soils and the food grown in them is also high because soils are derived from the weathering of local bedrock.

Groundwater may contain high amounts of natural radioactivity, mainly associated with uranium and thorium-rich soils and rocks, while surface water usually contains lower amounts of ^{222}Rn than groundwater.

Figure 2. Thorium series and the Uranium series (WNA, 2011)

Uranium (^{238}U) an ultimate progenitor of ^{222}Rn . It easily oxidizes in air, and becomes coated with a layer of oxide. Thus, uranium mainly occurs in oxidized form in nature.

The Uranium concentration in groundwater depends on lithology, geomorphology and other geological conditions of the region. In groundwater uranium is present both in dissolved and particulate form due to minerals such as Uranite, Pitchblende and Cornalite or as secondary mineral in the form of complex oxides of silicates phosphates, vanadates, lignite and monazite sands (Binesh and Arabshahi, 2011). Uranium is present in the earth's crust, principally in the hexavalent form. It is used primarily as a fuel in nuclear energy plants and is introduced into water supplies as a result of leaching from natural sources, from mill tailings, from emissions of the nuclear industry, from the combustion of coal and other fuels, and from phosphate fertilizers.

Although available information on concentrations in food and drinking-water is limited, it is likely that food is the principal source of intake of uranium in most areas. The decay products of uranium pass over 10 elements, all with very different chemical properties.

The ^{226}Ra is an alpha emitter, whose half-life is relatively long (1602 years), and it is the fifth member of the ^{238}U series. Radium exists in only the +2 oxidation state in solution and does not easily complex in water. Radium is one million times more radioactive than the same mass of uranium. Its decay occurs in at least seven stages, the following main products were called radium emanation recognized as radon.

The radon readily escapes from the soil or rock where it is generated and enters surrounding water or air. Radon, a noble gas, is essentially chemically inert. Unlike the other noble gases, radon has no known stable isotope. ^{222}Rn emits alpha particles as it spontaneously decays to a series of short-lived radioactive decay products. Radon isotope 222 has a half-life of 3.8 days, long enough to diffuse into the atmosphere through the solid rock or soil in which it is formed. This colorless, odorless, and chemically inactive gas is 7.6 times heavier than air; it readily dissolves in water, particularly if water is slightly acidic and not rich in minerals, and in alcohol and fatty acids. Alpha radiation with 5.49 MeV energy emitted by radon operates on short distance with penetration ability of about 41.1 μm in water and about 20 μm in tissue. Radon can enter a home via at least three common pathways:

Migration (up from the soil) into the basement through cracks and/or other openings in the foundation.

Release of dissolved radon gas from the household on-site water supply, some of the radon dissolved in tap water will escape to indoor air through common household activities such as showering, bathing, clothes washing, dish washing, and cooking. The proportion lost in this way will depend on circumstances.

Nevertheless, UNSCEAR has suggested that, as a general rule, radon in tap water gives rise to radon in room air at a concentration 10–4 lower than that in the water.

Release from building materials such as a granite block foundation, some fireplace materials, and floor or wall tiles

Radionuclide Determination Procedure in Sediment and Water

The results of an analytical determination can be no better than the sample used. Therefore, care must be taken when the sample is collected to assure that the sample truly represents the source.

Also, any changes that might occur within the sample between the time of collection and the time of analysis must be kept to a minimum. The methods employed to collect samples depend on several factors that differ with the type of investigation; nevertheless, certain criteria are of rather general application.

The preferred methods of sampling surface water are (1) integration through the cross section of a stream, or (2) depth integration at points on a suitable network laid out on a lake or reservoir. Note that a stream normally should not be sampled immediately after its confluence with another stream or after a waste outfall where mixing may not be adequate. Thorough mixing may require several miles, especially in wide, shallow, and slow streams. Wells, developed springs, and similar ground-water sources should be pumped before sampling to assure removal of stagnant water from the casing, pipes, and that part of the aquifer immediately adjacent to the well. Springs and seeps should be sampled as near the orifice as possible. These precautions should provide a sample that closely represents water typical of that in the undisturbed part of the aquifer. Criteria for sampling waste streams and other process solutions usually are dictated by the plant operations.

The water samples for the analysis can be taken from different sampling points each with a 100 centilitre bottle and acidified with 11M HCL solution at the rate of 10 ml per litre of sample. This is to eschew radionuclide absorption into the plastic container walls while it also releases any already absorbed radionuclide back into the samples. Water samples should be turned into marinelli beakers in the laboratory. Each marinelli beaker with a volume of 1 litre should first be rinsed with dilute Sulphuric Acid (H SO) and then the samples sealed and left for about 1 month so as to achieve a secular equilibrium state between the parent and daughter nuclides within each sample. After the achievement of secular equilibrium state the water samples can now be analyzed to determine the activity of the radionuclide present in each sample.

Samples of soil sediments are to be collected and processed according to the recommended procedure by the IAEA (1989). The soil samples should be air-dried for between 2–4 days, pulverized and homogenized by grinding it into powdery form. The powdered sample should be sieved using a 2mm sized mesh screen to obtain a fine texture of soil samples. The pulverized samples should later be oven-dried at 110°C until they attain a constant weight. The samples are to be stored for upward of 1 month before gamma activity counting, so as to ensure radioactive equilibrium between the long-lived radionuclides and their short-lived decay products. The samples storage for this period is necessary, because the activities of ^{238}U and ^{232}Th are to be measured by estimating ^{214}Bi and ^{208}Tl respectively (Singh *et al.* 2010).

Processes of Radionuclide Investigation in Sediments and Water

There are good number of methods and techniques used in the investigation of radioactive materials in sediments and water. Some of the methods are

1. Liquid Scintillation Method...Carbon-14, dissolved age; Tritium
2. Inorganic ion-exchange Method – Gamma counting...Cesium-137, dissolved
3. Gross Alpha and Gross Beta Radioactivity, dissolved and suspended – Residue Method

4. Chemical Separation and Precipitation Method....Lead-210, dissolved; Strontium-90, dissolved
5. Precipitation Method...Radium, dissolved as Radium-226
6. Radon Emanation Method.....Radium-226, dissolved
7. Distillation Method....Radio ruthenium, dissolved as ruthenium-106
8. Fluorometric Method – Direct.....Uranium, dissolved
9. Fluorometric Method – Extraction Procedure....Uranium, dissolved
10. Alpha Spectrometry – Chemical Separation....Uranium, dissolved, Isotopic ratios.
11. Gamma Spectroscopy, using NaTI detector.

The three basic and most common measurements/analyses in environmental radioactivity are:

1. In-situ Measurement: Background ionizing Radiation (BIR) using Radalert; a Geiger Muller tool.
2. Samples Collection (Soil, Water and Sediment) and Laboratory Analysis for Gross Alpha and Beta Radiation using gas field proportional counter.
3. Analysis for Gamma (Gamma Spectroscopy, using NaTI detector) of the samples

Instruments Applied in Radionuclide Presence Determination

1. Digilert 100 and 50 Nuclear Radiation Monitors. These are radiation measuring instruments used for in-situ measurement of background ionizing radiation (BIR) in environmental study. The combination of the two radiation monitoring meters was for high resolution, comparison of result and high sensitivity. The in situ approach of the background measurement is preferred and adopted to enable samples maintain their original environmental characteristics. The two radiation meters Digilert 50 and 100 nuclear radiation meters contain a Geiger Muller tube each capable of detecting alpha, beta, gamma, and X- rays within the temperature range of -10 to 50⁰C.
2. Sodium-Iodide NaI (TI) Scintillation Detector. The main purpose of this detector is to evaluate the specific activity contribution of the various radionuclides present in the samples analyzed having carried out the screening of the samples through gross alpha and beta activity measurement and using the Exploranium G R- 135 to identify the various radionuclides that contribute to the gross activities. The NaI (TI) gamma spectrometry system is employed to measure the radionuclide concentration of the samples because of the outstanding advantage of gamma rays spectrometry which lies in its ability to measure emitters directly in the original sample without the need for chemical separation. It also allows both the quantitative determination of the radionuclides.
3. The Proportional Counters. This equipment is used for the gross alpha and gross beta counting. It is a gas flow proportional counter with 450mg/cm³ thick window of diameter of 0.06m.
 - (a) Thin-Windows Proportional Counter. This counter can detect alpha and low energy beta radionuclides. It is less affected by contamination from loose residues and poor electrical conductance because the sample is outside.

- (b) Low Background Beta Counter. This is ionization for beta emitters having maximum energy of 0.3MeV. It is used to obtain background rate of 1cpm or less.
- (c) Internal Proportional Counter. The proportional counter as gas filled detectors operates on the principle of ionization of the counting gas by the incident radiation and subsequent charge collection at the electrodes. Internal proportional counters are suitable for determining the alpha activity at the alpha operating plateau and alpha/beta activity at the beta operating plateau. The alpha or beta activity or both can emanate from a single or several radionuclides.
4. The Exploranium G R-135Model. This is used for identifying the radionuclides present in the samples. It is a two way detector system utilizing NaI detector for high sensitivity and Geiger Muller (G-M) detector for extended dose rate range. It functions:
- (a) Search Dose Mode in which the G R-135 acts as search meter in counts per second as well as accumulated dose from the model was enabled. This mode is used to search for radioactive materials or carry out total count grid search.
- (b) Identify Mode- Nuclide Identification. In this mode the GR-135 accumulates spectral data from a sample and analyses the spectrum in terms of emitted energy level and net count contribution. The nuclides responsible for producing the spectrum are identified by comparison to a nuclide library and presented in tabular form.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Radionuclide presence in the sediments and water has both natural and man-made sources. There are various methods for the investigation of radioactivity in sediments and water. The results of an analytical determination can be no better than the sample used. Therefore, care must be taken when the sample is collected to assure that the sample truly represents the source.

Also, any changes that might occur within the sample between the times of collection, the time of analysis must be kept to a minimum. The methods used to collect samples will depend on several factors that differ with the type of investigation underway; however, certain criteria are of rather general application.

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